

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

NN 23

**20th International
Conference on
Nanosciences &
Nanotechnologies**

4-7 July 2023
Porto Palace Conference
Center & Hotel
Thessaloniki, Greece

2023

A Warm Welcome to the NN23!

The International Conference on Nanosciences and Nanotechnologies (NN23), is the internationally established world-class event in Nanosciences and Nanotechnologies (N&N) that focuses on the latest advances on N&N and promotes profound scientific discussions between scientists and researchers and innovators from different disciplines.

The Program of the 20th year of the International Conference on Nanosciences & Nanotechnologies at 5-8 July 2023 in Thessaloniki is a multidisciplinary collection of hot topics and a fine list of Invited Speakers related to the N&N fields, consisting of Invited, Oral presentations, poster presentations and running EU funded R&D Projects. These combined with the ISFOE International Symposium, the ISSON Summer Schools, the EXPO Exhibition and the B2B meetings that will take place in parallel within NANOTECHNOLOGY 2023, will provide to the participants access to a unique global network of innovators and specialists from the world academic, research and industrial communities.

Front-line experts from multidisciplinary research and application areas joined this conference, to discuss the benefits of N&N in their R&D efforts, to advance the networking and collaborating between different academia, research and industry players in the field and to stimulate the exchange of educational concepts.

NN23 targets the latest developments in the fields of Nanosciences & Nanotechnologies:

- **Plasmonics, Nanoelectronics & Clean Energy**
- **Nanomaterials, Nanofabrication, Nanoengineering & Nanocharacterization**
- **Nanomedicine**
- **Bioelectronics**
- **Graphene and other 2D Related Materials**

This year we are extremely proud to include in the NANOTECHNOLOGY 2023 and NN23, the

- **Workshop on In-line & Real-time Metrology and Quality Control for Nano-Manufacturing,**
- **Workshop on Computational Modeling of Materials, Devices & Processes**

On behalf of the NN23 Organizing and International Scientific Committees, we would like to thank you for your participation and support and we ensure that the NN23 presentations, discussions and Round Tables will expand our knowledge and form an outstanding platform for dynamic networking in the N&N fields.

It is our great pleasure to welcome you again to Thessaloniki and we hope that you will enjoy not only the insightful and interesting Scientific Program, but also the exciting networking and social events of NANOTECHNOLOGY 2023!

Best Regards

Professor S. Logothetidis
NN23 Chairman

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Virus-based enzymatic nanoreactors for enzyme replacement therapy

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Enzyme replacement therapy (ERT) has been used to treat a few of the many existing diseases which are originated from the lack of, or low enzymatic activity. Exogenous enzymes are administered to contend with the enzymatic activity deficiency. Enzymatic nanoreactors based on the enzyme encapsulation inside of virus-like particles (VLPs) appear as an interesting alternative for ERT. VLPs are excellent delivery vehicles for therapeutic enzymes as they are biodegradable, uniformly organized, and porous nanostructures that transport and could protect the biocatalyst from the external environment without much affecting the bioactivity. Consequently, significant efforts have been made in the production processes of virus-based enzymatic nanoreactors and their functionalization, which are here presented. The use of virus-based enzymatic nanoreactors for the treatment of lysosomal storage diseases such as Gaucher, Fabry, and Pompe diseases, as well as potential therapies for galactosemia, and Hurler and Hunter syndromes will be discussed.

[1] Chauhan K., Olivares-Medina C.N., Villagrana-Escareño M.V., Juárez-Moreno K.O., Cadena-Nava R.D., Rodríguez-Hernández A.G. and Vazquez-Duhalt R. (2023) Targeted enzymatic VLP-nanoreactors with β -glucocerebrosidase activity as potential enzyme replacement therapy for Gaucher's disease. *ChemMedChem* 17: e202300384

[2] Gama P., Cadena-Nava R.D., Juárez-Moreno K., Pérez-Robles J. and Vazquez-Duhalt R. (2021) Virus-based nanoreactors containing GALT activity for classic galactosemia therapy. *ChemMedChem* 16: 1438– 1445.

[3] González-Davis O., Villagrana-Escareño M.V., Trujillo M.A., Gama P., Chauhan K. and Vazquez-Duhalt R. (2023) Virus-like nanoparticles as enzyme carriers for enzyme replacement therapy (ERT). *Virology* (In press).

pH- and Redox-Responsive Cancer Nanotheranostics Based on Cyclodextrin-Capped Mesoporous Silica

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Versatile chemical modalities for multi-step surface functionalization of mesoporous silica nanoparticle (MSN) open a plethora of possibilities for devising nanosystems for applications in targeted cancer therapy and imaging. Herein, recent research efforts on the development of multifunctionalized MSN-based nanotherapeutics for targeted treatment and imaging of glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) are described. MSN's surface was functionalized with GBM-targeting biomolecules, while further surface functionalization was performed to endow the materials with linkers that are cleavable in the weakly acidic microenvironment of tumors or in the presence of tumor-overexpressed glutathione (GSH). The entrapment of cargo molecules (dyes, anticancer drugs or contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)) within MSN's pores was achieved by binding cyclodextrin analogues to the pH- or GSH-cleavable linkers on the MSN's surface. The release kinetics of cargo molecules was monitored by UV/Vis and fluorescence measurements, and an enhanced cargo release in the weakly acidic environment and upon exposure to GSH was observed. Furthermore, MSNs containing gadolinium-based contrast agents were evaluated for possible imaging of tumor tissue in MRI. Biological activity of MSNs was investigated using U87 (GBM) cell line, while their cellular uptake ability was evaluated by confocal microscopy and flow cytometry. The research results evidence the promising potential of the developed MSNs for their application as GBM-targeted theranostic nanoparticle.

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